

How do metamorphic fluids influence metamorphic rock time records?

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The modern field of petrochronology has made significant advances in linking “age to stage” and “date to rate” over the last decade. Through application of petrochronological techniques, it has become increasingly obvious that metamorphic cycles take place over tens of millions of years. The extent to which metamorphism proceeds as a series of steps or as more of a continuous process in different lithologies and different tectonic settings is still unclear.

Crustal fluids – including silicate melts and hydrous fluids – play an important, but not always fully considered, role in catalysing and driving chronometer reactions. Fluids may promote crystallisation, thus starting the record, or may erase or erode an earlier history through promoting dissolution, alteration or thermal disturbance. The result can be a patchy geochronological record across a sample suite, which might appear recorded as one protracted event rather than individual stages. This contribution will explore how combinations of geochronological data, independent geochemical datasets, petrological observations and modelling provide a strong foundation to constrain the timing, timescales and pulsed or continuous evolution of metamorphic processes to be constrained more tightly.

This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 956127